

Exploring Identity, Gender, and Generational Conflicts in 1950s and 1960s Hollywood Melodrama: A Cinematic Analysis of Douglas Sirk's "All That Heaven Allows" and Vincente Minnelli's "Home from the Hill"

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the complex interplay of identity crisis, generational conflict, gender conflict, and sexual repression as depicted in Hollywood melodramatic films of the 1950s and 1960s. Focusing on Douglas Sirk's "All That Heaven Allows" and Vincente Minnelli's "Home from the Hill," the study analyzes how melodrama serves as an expressive cinematic form that portrays individual lives and emphasizes subjective viewpoints within a bourgeois setting. Through examining mise-en-scène, performance, and narrative techniques, the paper reveals how these films articulate deeply conflicting socio-political themes in a society marked by political censorship and constrained morality regulations. By addressing issues such as patriarchal authority, familial legitimacy, and the repression of female sexuality, the study underscores the enduring relevance of melodrama in highlighting societal tensions and ideological failures. The plot is led by a female point of view, which delivers satisfaction even though social and sexual difficulties are not always resolved. As Nowell-Smith points out, the relevance of melodrama stems from its "ideological failure."

Keywords: Melodrama, identity crisis, gender conflict, Douglas Sirk, Vincente Minnelli

Introduction:

Melodrama, as an artistic, aesthetic, and expressive form of cinematic representation, not only depicts the lives of individuals in society but also emphasizes their subjective viewpoints by bringing up questions of identity and addressing them in a bourgeois setting. Color, light, decor, shadow, editing, gestures, camera angles, music, and other cinematic components are employed as interactive aesthetic metaphors to tackle profoundly conflicting socio-political themes in a society dominated by political censorship and constrained morality regulations. This paper examines the concerns of identity crisis that melodrama illustrates, primarily generational conflict, gender conflict, and sensitive issues of sexual repression, through the cinematic mode by intentionally using mise-en-scène, performance, and narrative techniques, by looking at domestic melodramas, namely Douglas Sirk's *All That Heaven Allows* and Vincente Minnelli's *Home from the Hill*.

Literature Review :

Hollywood melodramatic films of the 50s and 60s revolved around emotionally charged family situations in which more significant sociopolitical conflicts are conveyed in personal terms through the 'structure of experience' (Elsaesser, 1987: 47). The individuals that resided within these familial frames were associated by private property passed down through the generations, highlighting the significance of patriarchal authority which acted as a catalyst for generational conflicts and issues foregrounding 'question of law or legitimacy' (Nowell-Smith, 1987: 71). Drawing on Freudian 'family romance,' the Hollywood melodrama underlined the difficulties of a child establishing a 'sexual identity within the family' [Nowell-Smith in Minnelli and Melodrama, 1987: 73], under the protection of a symbolic law that the father represented by functioning as the perpetrator of this symbolic sexual division. This also raises issues of individual identity within the family and bourgeois

society, which typically requires sacrifice. The happy ending and resolution are often achieved at the expense of repression and castration and siphoning out of the excess that is difficult to accommodate. With the characters' restricted and limited dramatic function, the formal devices and mise-en-scene provide the spectator with a central point of orientation. The setting and decor of the narrative in a claustrophobic atmosphere of bourgeois home and the banalities of objects, contrasted with expressed emotions, epitomize the relation of decor to character.

Vincente Minnelli's *Home from the Hill* (1960) is a family melodrama that is set in Texas and revolves around Wade Hunnicutt - the brutal patriarch; Hannah Hunnicutt - his stern yet suffering wife; Theron Hunnicutt - their sheltered son and Rafe Copley as Wade's illegitimate son, uses the motifs of the family romance like problems of legitimacy, feudal lords, puberty etc to articulate issues of generational conflict by opposing the old order through the succeeding generation. Through the character of Theron Hunnicutt as the adolescent child desiring liberation from his parents, the film critiques the parents' feudal class to challenge it as a legitimate basis of idealization.

With his 40,000 acres, Wade owns most of the town. He is a man of conflicting desires and ambitions. His authority is derived from his position in the feudal order, critiqued by Wade's presentation as a masculine figure with unyielding excess. He's feared and despised more than he is respected because of his womanizing nature. He "owns the men's land. But he also wants their wives" (Cordova, 1987: 258). Throughout the film, Wade blabbers about what makes a man, smoking his pipe, shooting guns, and swaggering with his big, muscular physique, which makes him an intimidating and enormous presence. Whether sitting open-legged in his trophy-filled den or pushing through a crowd, he commands space and fills it like a man who cannot be contained. Hannah appears to be the only figure resistant to this exploitation. After keeping her son away from his influence for seventeen years, she eventually has to give in to Wade's demand of making "a man out of" Theron to ensure his "lineage and generational continuity" (1987: 258).

Theoron's transition from being the 'mamma's boy' to his father's son can be traced back to the spatial differences between his room, which is filled with books, butterflies, stamps, and telescopes, and his father's den with rifles, booze, hunted trophies where Wade takes him to "show how a man lives" that is used to create generational polarization. The subsequent hunting scene solidifies Theoron's identification with his father. This momentarily identification is profoundly transformed with the revelation of Rafe as Wade's illegitimate son, which Cordova points out as being similar to Freud's family romance: "Theoron's rebellion against his father is on other grounds as well [...] Theoron deny the validity of the family and refuse to further the family name [...] Theoron's disidentification with his father is a disidentification with him as exploiter" (259). Despite his best efforts to distance himself from his father's identity and legitimacy, he eventually ends up being a version of his father by "fathering a child without taking responsibility for it" thereby failing to break free from the old order (259). Eventually, through the illegitimate son Rafe, the new order of a privatized family, which has nothing to do with class difference, is established.

Gender Conflict and Sexual Repression:

Another essential conflict evident in the 50s and 60s melodramatic films was between masculine and feminine. The Classic Hollywood films portrayed women as 'receptacles' but the melodrama genre, by featuring women as protagonists, gave space to women characters to represent their desires and to articulate their point of view "where the central figure is a man, and there is regularly an impairment of his masculinity" (1987: 72). Centred around the family placed in the context of working of patriarchy, the melodramatic film touches on "sensitive areas of sexual repression and frustration" by highlighting the conflicts among individuals connected by bonds of love (Mulvey, 1987: 75). The use of dramatic mise-en-scene, which generates a complex visual pattern that filmmakers actively deploy to communicate these issues, becomes a crucial element in expressing the female characters' inner dilemmas and complications, their bottled up feelings, resentment, disaffection and also their sexual desires.

Mulvey sees two points of view in melodramas: male and female. While the female protagonist's viewpoint "acts as a source of identification," it also produces an excess that cannot be accommodated (1987: 76). The male point of view investigates familial difficulties and sexist fantasies that are attempted to be rectified:

For family life to survive, a compromise has to be reached, sexual differences softened, and the male brought to see the value of domestic life. As art and drama deal generously with male fantasy, a dramatic rendering of women's frustrations, publicly acting out an adjustment of balance in the male ego is socially and ideologically beneficial. A positive male figure who rejects rampant virility and opposes the relentless power of the father achieves (at least employing a happy end) the reintegration of both sexes in family life. The phallogentric, castration-based, more misogynist fantasies of patriarchal culture are here in contradiction with the ideology of the family and melodrama, sacrificed in the interests of civilization and reaffirmation of the Oedipus complex. [Laura Mulvey in Notes On Sirk and Melodrama, 1987: 76.]

The familial order is consolidated in the imagery of patriarchal power, generating a frame of reference for articulating disagreements through the establishment of a series of symbolic distinctions that highlight issues of sexual identity, which is typically established through social identification. By confining sexuality to the institution of marriage, where men resume the authoritarian role of their fathers and women are taken into account by their relationships with men as husbands, daughters, mothers, and so on, the domestic environment simultaneously legitimizes and conceals sexuality. The melodramatic protagonist's restlessness and sexual angst, as well as the unanticipated breakout of violence, conveyed psychologically, all contribute to the issues connected to gender identity: "From impotence to hysteria and from alcoholic depression to full-blown psychoses, the domestic melodrama runs the full gamut of psychological disorders" (Rodowick, 1987: 272). The female characters are divided into two categories: "passive suffering heroines and turbulent sexual rebels" who are only identifiable in patriarchal authority interactions by their 'systematic exclusion,' which relates to the patriarchal authority's

supposed right to give social and sexual identity (1987: 272). Female characters' conflicts arise from the difficulty of subordinating and channeling feminine sexuality according to the passive functions defined by patriarchy, namely heterosexual marriage, and motherhood, as opposed to male characters' conflicts, which arise from the difficulty of achieving an active sexual identity through which patriarchal power can be represented. In this way, feminine sexuality always exceeds the societal institutions that attempt to limit it.

Melodrama films also fail to accommodate this excess and 'undischarged emotion' of internal repression of female characters within the narrative structure of the film and instead rely on elements of *mise-en-scene* such as music, dance, lighting, colors, visual orchestration, decor, and also the actor's performance- the intonation in their voice, their emasculated gestures, hysterical outburst replacing self-annihilating action, portraying internal conflict and expressions to "heighten the emotionality" of the action. As Nowell-Smith points out, since melodramatic conventions are similar to realism, the hysteria can be identified as a moment where the realist representative convention breaks down: "Realist representation cannot accommodate the fantasy, just as the bourgeois society cannot accommodate its realization.

Before delving into the investigation of 1950s family melodramas to see how the factors outlined above are employed in these films to emphasize these concerns of gender and sexual repression, it is crucial to understand the historical background of the post-war period in America in which these films are situated. The United States had substantial economic and industrial expansion following WWII and a burgeoning urban population in the expanding suburbs of major cities. The greater freedom of women during the war years had to be balanced against the employment needs of men returning home, and women were urged to return to more conventional roles as spouses and mothers. The promise of democratic capitalism and a free market system that would provide wealth contributed to re-establishing social identities. The developing structure of bureaucracy and authority, which limited individual activity, contrasted this. There was also growing concern that the next challenge to society structure would come from within, through

the corruption of democratic beliefs from the inside. With a better grasp of Freudianism, a society emerged that, ironically, accepted the values of conventional family life. The film industry was not immune to post-war America's fast expansion, and it found itself competing for audience share with television, which was growing in popularity. The industry's response was to make more use of new technical advancements like widescreen and color and to target key demographic groups like women and teenagers who had previously been identified as key consumers. It is in this context that I would be looking at the films that are now regarded collectively as domestic melodramas, in particular, Douglas Sirk's *All That Heaven Allows* as an 'aesthetic ideology' that "barricades itself within an already eroding myth of a society founded on the centrality of the family and patriarchal power".

Sirk and his films continue to be at the center of the melodrama discussion in cinema. The notion that Sirk's films portray underlying societal tensions became fundamental to a broader discussion about 1950s Hollywood cinema, which has since been seen as portraying the symptoms of a deeper crisis in post-war American society. *All That Heaven Allows* follows Cary Scott, an affluent suburban widow who begins an affair with Ron Kirby, her young gardener from a lower class. Their relationship becomes the topic of local gossip among Cary's neighbors. Cary's two adult children oppose her marriage plans, forcing her to choose between giving up her younger lover or losing her children. Cary chooses motherhood over desire and abandons Ron. When her children declare that they are both leaving home regardless, the absurdity of her self-sacrifice becomes evident. An accident brings the couple back together, and Cary is left to nurse the crippled Ron back to health.

In Sirk's films, the objects surrounding the characters appear packed with significance and importance; everything in the frame has value, giving the images a suffocating effect at times. In *All That Heaven Allows*, Cary is frequently seen surrounded by meaning-laden artifacts in her lavish house. Mirrors are another frequent theme in Sirk's works, regularly appearing as an integral part of the *mise-en-scene*. We observe characters staring at mirrors when they

follow society's ideals, play a part, or are delusionary about themselves. Mirrors are iconic in his melodramas because they represent illusion and delusion.

Sirk's use of 'frames inside frames' has become a well-known visual technique. Characters are frequently enclosed by mirror frames, entrances, windows, picture frames, and ornamental screens. These techniques show that characters are alone or imprisoned in their lonely lives or that their environments continue to oppress them. Rather than attempting to express the atmosphere of a scene or a figure with more organic lighting, extreme artificial lighting effects are achieved via the use of shadows and colored filters. In another scene, Cary has an emotional chat with her daughter Kay, who has been the object of derision due to her mother's relationship with the gardener Ron Kirby. The action occurs in Kay's bedroom, which is dominated by a circular window that lets in an unnaturally bright rainbow light. This lighting effect suggests a stained-glass window appearance and serves as an expressionistic metaphor for the dialogue. Cary knows that she must end her relationship with Ron as she listens to her weeping daughter. The lighting effect here represents not just her sexual urge being repressed but also the realization that her love for Ron is hopeless.

All That Heaven Allows depicts four main stylistic and narrative issues: subversive societal critique, Cary's repression, Ron Kirby's alternative, and the problematic happy ending, which reveals the gender conflict and sexual repression issues that this paper seeks to examine. Cary is a widowed mother of two grown children. She goes to the neighboring country club with her date, the elderly Harvey, after being invited for drinks by her friend Sarah. Cary's children and the rest of the town think Harvey would be a nice match for her widowed mother because he is single. For example, Cary's daughter Kay deduces from Freud that Harvey is a suitable companion since he poses no sexual threat. On the other hand, Cary's status is questioned by the community, represented by Mona at the club. Cary chooses to wear a red evening gown, illustrating her new status as a single and available woman, a choice that has already been commented upon by Ned, her son. At the club, Mona

echoes Ned's unease, saying, "There's nothing like red for attracting attention."

In the film's first part, Cary is depicted as a victim, oppressed by society's rigorous standards, her gender position as a widow, wife, and mother, her family's constraints, and her own convictions. Cary's subjugation is vividly depicted through the mise-en-scene, particularly in the domestic environment where she is most frequently found. The Scotts' house is shown as a lavish tomb for Cary's dead husband. The room, for instance, is dominated by a massive fireplace filled with Mr Scott's sports trophies and a marbled mirror that covers the whole wall. The usage of mirrors and reflections throughout the film reflects Cary's oppressed and secluded position. Cary is shown at her dressing table after her first encounter with Ron, gazing at her own reflection. Her children get home at this time and are presented visually, captured in the reflection of their mother in the mirror, emphasizing the oppressive nature of their connection. The Scott mansion appears full of harsh reflective surfaces, which brutally represent Cary's isolation and alienation from her surroundings, owing to these mise-en-scene features.

Ron Kirby, Cary's gardener, provides an alternative to Cary's lonely and solitary existence. He initially appears outside, tending to Cary's trees, clad in warm, earthy-colored clothing in contrast to Cary's gray suit and Sara's artificiality. Ron is described as mysterious and aloof in their first meeting, uninterested in the niceties of the polite conversation that Cary tries to engage him in. Even though he is younger and appears to be more free-thinking than Cary, Ron maintains a dismissive attitude towards her, forcing her to choose between the life and stability she has known and his 'new' way of life. Cary is the person who is required to compromise and make sacrifices as a widow, wife, and mother. A quick and unusual chain of events eventually joins the pair, but the nature of their ultimate union makes this closure even more difficult. As Laura Mulvey points out, the ending, with Ron crippled and Cary nursing him, shows Cary reverting towards a more socially acceptable position as Ron's mother instead of the couple's happy union:

"How can a mother of grown children overcome the taboo against her continued sexual activity in 'civilized society,' when the object of her desire is reduced to child-like dependence on her ministrations?"

Conclusion:

Melodrama may be seen as a paradoxical intersection where identity, gender, sexuality, and generational issues are addressed in an artistic form through technical, performative, and narrative frameworks. The plot is led by a female point of view, which delivers satisfaction even though social and sexual difficulties are not always resolved. As Nowell-Smith points out, the relevance of melodrama stems from its "ideological failure." It opens a space that other Hollywood forms have closed off because it "cannot accommodate its problems" and instead exposes them in all their blatant inconsistencies.

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